

More Than Just Tweets: The Potential of Alternative Geo-Social Media Data for Disaster Management

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Abstract

Natural disasters are increasingly prevalent worldwide, necessitating the utilisation of diverse datasets for effective disaster response. While geo-social media data represents a valuable resource in this context, the recent restrictions to Twitter data have significantly impacted its availability for disaster research. Alternative social media platforms to Twitter remain underexplored, leading to limited understanding of their potential. To address this gap, we collected posts for a specific use case, Hurricane Ian, from four social media platforms (Mastodon, Reddit, Telegram, and TikTok), and subsequently geoparsed each post. We then computed spatial and temporal patterns and evaluated their correlations to investigate the potential applicability of other data sources for disaster response efforts. While none of the platforms can fully substitute Twitter’s role in disaster management, the findings demonstrated that substantial amounts of potentially valuable data can be sourced from other platforms. Despite consistent overall patterns, subtle differences in temporal activity and spatial distribution suggest that each platform offers unique insights that enhance situational awareness. However, a significant challenge in using these platforms for disaster response is the low spatial accuracy achievable through geoparsing.

Keywords: geo-social media, Telegram, Tik Tok, Reddit, Mastodon, disaster management

1 Introduction

Social media platforms are widely regarded as valuable sources of big data for a range of scientific applications, including sociology, communication studies, and environmental research [13]. The integration of both textual and visual content, along with associated metadata, has provided valuable insights into societal patterns, cultural dynamics, as well as geographic phenomena [47, 69]. The geospatial component extends the use of social media data into critical domains such as disaster management, where location-based information plays a crucial role [16, 37]. Understanding the spatial distribution of hazards, exposure, and

vulnerabilities is vital for effective risk assessment, emergency response, and mitigation strategies [81].

Geotagging and geoparsing are two primary techniques used to determine geographic locations from social media posts. Geotagging relies on Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) services embedded in source devices to capture precise geographic coordinates or manual tagging of locations. However, most social media platforms do not support geotagging, necessitating the identification of location mentions for spatial analyses. This so-called geoparsing involves two steps: Location Entity Recognition (LER) and subsequent geocoding [44]. LER identifies location names, such as cities or addresses, within the unstructured text of a social media post. The subsequent geocoding process converts them into geographic coordinates, making the data usable for spatial analysis.

Despite the widespread use of social media in disaster management, much of the current research focuses on single-platform analysis [32, 77, 17], leading to a potential "single-platform data bias" that can skew the results, as different platforms might provide unique perspectives on the same event [76]. This is influenced by differing platform structures [70], differences in user behaviours and demographics [62], unique spatial and temporal characteristics of the data [45], and the specific structure of metadata [75] on each platform.

Twitter (now: X), in particular, has been one of the most widely used platforms for disaster-related studies, due to its open Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) with easy access to geotagged data for research purposes. However, recent changes to Twitter's API in May 2023, which restricted data access for research purposes, have severely impacted its longstanding role as the default platform for developing and validating new scientific methods [50]. Similar events in the past have prompted discussions about the emergence of the so-called "Post-API age" [19] and "APIcalypse" [10], a scenario where researchers face significant challenges due to the lack of accessible data.

This study directly addresses two gaps in disaster management research: the overreliance on a single platform and the challenges caused by restricted data access. Specifically, we investigate the potential of underexplored social media platforms with an open API — TikTok, Telegram, Mastodon, and Reddit - as sources of geospatial information in a disaster context. To this end, we present workflows to strategically access data from the different platforms. As no platform allows for explicit spatial queries, we employed a geoparsing approach to extract locations from the post texts and thus assign georeferences to the acquired posts. By comparing the geospatial and temporal patterns across these platforms and with georeferenced Twitter data, this study evaluates their potential contributions, differing data acquisition workflows, and limitations. Our aim is to identify and establish generalisable methods for data extraction and analysis in order to have meaningful alternatives for the no longer available Twitter data in geo-social media research in the future. With this study, we therefore aim to answer the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** Which social media platform is a viable alternative for georeferenced Twitter data in disaster research?

- **RQ2:** How much do the spatial characteristics of disaster-related posts from various social media platforms differ?

In our study, we refer to a single use case in the USA, the world region with the highest number of geo-social media research [82], mainly due to its historically high availability of Twitter data. Consequently, we assumed that data availability on other social media platforms would also be higher and lead to less selection bias. We chose to analyse Hurricane Ian, that struck Florida in September 2022. It was the deadliest natural disaster in Florida in almost 100 years, affecting large parts of the Caribbean and the Southern states, including Georgia, South Carolina, and North Carolina [33]. The event was selected since it predates the changes in Twitter’s API policies and therefore allows for a direct comparison to the widely researched Twitter data.

2 Related work

2.1 Social media platforms in natural disasters

Social media has long provided valuable information for disaster management across pre-disaster, response, and post-disaster phases. Early evidence of its utility dates back to the 2007 California fires [21], with the 2010 Haiti earthquake often recognised as the first major event demonstrating the use of social media for natural disaster response [6]. A bibliographic analysis of disaster-related social media papers highlights Twitter as the second most frequent keyword, after “social media” and before “disaster” [17]. While studies on natural disasters using data from other platforms exist, they are less common.

There are a handful of studies using data from TikTok, Instagram, Facebook, or Telegram: [43] analyse emotional responses about wildfires in Hawaii from 526 TikTok videos and 59,950 comments, focusing on narrative analysis. In a study about the same event, [72] categorise 275 TikTok videos into the temporal categories “during the disaster”, “immediate aftermath” and “long-term recovery” and show that videos containing misinformation had the highest engagement. [4] investigate user interactions, such as views and comments, for 100 climate change-related TikTok videos. [8] analyse Instagram posts on wildfires in Tasmania with an emphasis on the visual representation of the event, which is found to be mostly aesthetically pleasing. [46] employ data from Instagram to geo-locate digital humanitarian activities in Australia in a qualitative approach. In a study on Hurricane Ian, which is also the use case in this paper, [58] employ Facebook population data to devise an index for the evacuation rate in a region. However, their study does not utilise any textual data. [41] analyses the usefulness of Facebook’s Safety Check during a typhoon through interviews. Similarly, another study investigates the capacity of Telegram for sending warning messages in the event of a disaster [22]. [59] collect 12,000 Telegram posts from 361 channels about the 2019 Iranian floods and manually assign topics. Additionally, they identify the toponyms mentioned, showing that certain provinces are referred to more frequently on different days. To summarise,

social media-based studies about natural disasters that do not employ Twitter data generally work with very small datasets, employ qualitative or manual methods, and neglect the spatial dimension of the data.

Cross-platform analyses include the comparison of public earthquake-related discourse between Twitter and Reddit [62], showing different topics and sentiments on the platforms. Similar differences for sentiments are also found in a comparative study between Twitter and Telegram for the 2019 Iranian floods [59]. However, these quantitative studies do not focus on the spatial characteristics of the data. Additionally, more qualitative studies have explored disaster communication across multiple platforms, such as Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok [73].

2.2 Geotagging and geoparsing

The popularity of Twitter in disaster research can be attributed to the possibility of explicit geotagging, which can provide reasonably accurate spatial data and thus generate situational awareness. Despite the 2019 removal of precise geotagging limiting the data’s spatial accuracy [30], researchers could still use the “place” attribute of Twitter data for spatial analyses [38], which mostly provided bounding boxes of locations (e.g. cities). Twitter datasets were subject to sampling biases, as only 1-3% of posts contain geolocation data [56], and the geotagging behaviour varies by region [31]. Moreover, researchers could only access a limited historical window, often restricting datasets to 1% of all Tweets via the real-time Streaming API [3, 78].

To address these limitations and augment the size of datasets, researchers have turned to geoparsing techniques, which infer location from text. Geoparsing includes LER, with many studies relying on spaCy and Stanford Named Entity Recognition (NER) tools [34]. Recently, geoparsing pipelines have progressed to BERT-based LER and geo-knowledge-guided GPT models [74, 29]. Despite these advances, many studies still use spaCy due to its speed and resource efficiency [48]. For instance, [67] propose a spaCy-based approach to distinguish between the current position of a user and remote locations. LER has also been applied to texts from other platforms like Reddit and Telegram, with studies fine-tuning algorithms for these contexts [25, 2, 80].

3 Methodology

To compare the use of different social media platforms in the disaster context, we employed a platform-specific approach for data collection, leveraging APIs from Twitter, TikTok, Reddit, Telegram, and Mastodon. These platforms were selected based on their prominence in existing research, their substantial and diverse user bases, growth potential, and the accessibility of their APIs. We then filtered the identified texts for the keyword ‘hurricane’ and performed geoparsing to extract spatial information. Figure 1 provides a high-level overview of our study workflow.

Figure 1: Overview of study workflow. The logos of the social media platforms are taken from Wikimedia Commons.

3.1 Data acquisition

Data collection was focused on the period from September 20 to October 10, 2022, which we determined by analysing posting frequencies on Twitter to capture the pre- and post-disaster phases of Hurricane Ian. Table 1 compares crawling options and general characteristics for the platforms in question.

Table 1: Comparison of Social Media Data Retrieval Options (April 2025).

	Twitter	TikTok	Reddit	Telegram	Mastodon
Geolocation	Yes	Country	No	No	No
Free for research?	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Historical retrieval	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes ^a	Yes
Historical rate limit^b	<300k	Varies ^e	<100k	<1,000	~200
Historical filtering	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Real-time retrieval	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes ^c
Real-time rate limit^d	1%	Varies ^e / 100%	100% ^c	100%	100%

^a Up to 1,000 records per query, without pagination.

^b Number of posts per day; for Telegram, number of chats; for Reddit, per query.

^c Webhook for a few, predefined chats.

^d Percentage of retrieved posts of all generated posts.

^e Free tier returns 1,500 posts per month combining historical and real-time endpoints. For \$100, one could get 10,000 posts per month, again combining all endpoints.

3.1.1 Twitter

Twitter (now: X) is a microblogging platform launched in July 2006. Due to its large user base, easily accessible APIs and the option to fetch posts based on geolocations, it has been the most popular platform for geo-social media research. Together with Weibo, its Chinese counterpart, Twitter was a data source for over 70% of papers utilising location-based social media data [47].

In late 2022, Twitter was purchased by Elon Musk, which heavily influenced its data availability for research purposes and user base [66]. In early 2023, API access for research purposes was put behind a paywall, which represented a major turning point in social media-based research [50]. As X has not provided any data for research purposes since its rebranding, we purposefully continue to

use the previous name "Twitter" throughout this paper.

Before this API shutdown, Twitter data with georeferences could be retrieved via REST and Streaming APIs. However, only a fraction of all Tweets had geolocations, either in the form of a point coordinate or - in the majority of cases - as a bounding box of a 'place' with varying degrees of spatial accuracy [38, 27]. Additionally, it was only possible to retrieve a sample of Tweets from the last seven days for research purposes [26]. Starting in 2021, an API for historic data was available [53].

For the purpose of this study, we collected geotagged Twitter data via the Recent Search and Filtered Stream endpoints of the Twitter API v2. Employing spatial filtering, using a bounding box ($POLYGON((-94.26\ 23.12, -72.64\ 23.12, -72.64\ 38.16, -94.26\ 38.16, -94.26\ 23.12))$), and temporal filtering for the time period between September 20 and October 10 2022, we were able to collect 2,798,478 geotagged Tweets.

3.1.2 TikTok

TikTok is a Chinese video-sharing social networking service launched in September 2016, which has gained significant popularity worldwide among younger demographics for its short videos [49], while being criticised for its data privacy handling [51]. There has been plenty research about TikTok and its societal impact, with a focus on the USA and China and the disciplines of psychology, health, and communication science [61]. However, TikTok has not established itself as a source for geo-social media data in research. So far, there have been only been a handful of studies, including on the attempted 2022 Peruvian coup [54] and a tobacco product ban in the USA [18].

Since 2023, there is a Research API to collect TikTok data for research purposes. At the time of this paper, however, it could only be used by researchers from selected countries who are enrolled at least as doctoral students. So far, only fragmentary information from the TikToks can be accessed, including the description under the videos. It is not (yet) possible to acquire the videos themselves. The TikTok Research API provides access to eight endpoints, each of which can be queried using POST requests. The *videos* endpoint, for instance, allows users to filter posts based on a predefined threshold or an exact value for various attributes. Using the attribute *region_code*, queries can be restricted to data from specific countries. The API imposes a daily request quota of 1,000 requests, with a maximum of 100 videos per request. However, in practice, this maximum number of requests is lower due to restrictions on private content and posts from underage users. One major limitation of the TikTok API is that it is not possible to fetch posts for up to 48 hours after they were created, which significantly reduces potential of the platform in the immediate response phase of the disaster management cycle.

This study only utilised the *videos* API endpoint for data acquisition. All posts published between September 20 and October 10 2022, with the *region_code* for the US and keywords or hashtags containing "hurricane" were queried. We were able to collect information for 168,761 TikToks. These videos

had a total of 6,522,670 comments. 37% of the posts did not have any comments, while 12.7% had more than 10 comments. However, due to rate limits, we were not able to access the comments.

3.1.3 Reddit

Reddit is a discussion website that was founded in 2005 and is organised into interest-based communities, so-called *subreddits*. With its diverse user base and extensive range of topics, it is a dynamic platform. So far, Reddit data has mostly been used for research in the disciplines of computer science, health, and social science [55].

Accessing Reddit data via an API has been possible since 2008. In early 2023, following the release of several Large Language Models (LLMs) trained on Reddit data, rate limits were raised substantially and any kind of monetisation from Reddit content was forbidden. The API remains free for research purposes, although it only allows 100 requests per minute [60]. To assemble a comprehensive dataset, fetching historical data from existing Reddit archives is also possible [64]. These are generally created by accessing submissions and comments in real-time and storing them partitioned by months. While this scraping does not comply with Reddit’s terms of services, such archived data has been used for research purposes. To obtain data from archives, various online torrent services (e.g. Academic Torrents, Pastebin) can be used. The most well-known archive is Pushshift, which even had its own API to query historical data [5]. At the time of this study, this API was only available to Reddit moderators, while other researchers could only download monthly dumps. To filter this huge amount of data, submissions and comments from specific subreddits can be gathered [7], content of submissions and comments filtered separately [62], or both filtering techniques combined [24].

This study filtered downloaded Reddit submission archive dumps by attributes. Subsequently, the comments archive was filtered to only retrieve comments associated with the selected submissions. For this case study, the word “*hurricane*” was chosen as filter criterion in the title or body of the submission, as well as a publication date between September 20 and October 20, 2022. From a total of four archives, a dataset comprised of 31,187 submissions and 169,861 comments could be retrieved.

3.1.4 Telegram

Telegram is a messaging platform that was launched in 2013. It allows its users to create and join public chats for specific interests, as well as private messaging. *Channels* have administrators that broadcast content to subscribers. In contrast, in *groups*, members can interact with each other, allowing for many-to-many communication [52]. Telegram has become popular due to its robust encryption features [14], strong data privacy policies, and tolerance for any kind of content. These factors have attracted users who are opposed to using mainstream communication platforms. Many studies using data from Telegram

thus have a strong political focus, such as the analysis of public discourse on the 2017 Iranian elections [36] and political extremism in the US [79].

Telegram offers a dedicated API with several endpoints to extract data, which can be accessed through the *Teleton* library in Python. However, only a few of those endpoints can be used to collect text messages, with the chat-wise structure of the platform complicating the data collection process. In order to access a post, the name or ID of the channel needs to be included in the request. To overcome this issue, snowball sampling has been proposed in the literature. This crawling strategy starts with an initial set of chats, from which other referenced chats are gathered and subsequently crawled. [5] use this approach to gather over 317 million messages from 27,801 chats, starting from groups related to right-wing politics and cryptocurrency. The amount of messages that can be collected daily is highly dependent on the number of messages in a chat, since the API endpoint is limited to 200 chats. While Telegram does not impose any rules on collecting historical data, global real-time data collection is not feasible due to its chat-based structure. This also imposes one fundamental issue related to the deletion messages, which can introduce a significant bias to the analysis [11].

The crawler utilised in this study also followed the snowball approach: For each input channel or group, it retrieved and stored messages, as well as meta-data about the chat. Additionally, it generated a list of mentioned chats from messages that had been forwarded to the chat and explicit links to other chats. This list served as the input for the subsequent crawling iteration. This process was repeated until a specified time limit or iteration number was reached.

To collect data for Hurricane Ian, 18 disaster-related and 3 US-based input chats were identified manually and crawled in two separate processes. Starting from the disaster-related chats (see Table 2), 11 million messages were gathered from a total of 912 chats. The second crawling process collected over 41 million messages from more than 1,900 chats. One drawback from the snowballing approach is that it is difficult to determine when to terminate the data acquisition. The first run was stopped based on the assumption that there would not be more than 1,000 disaster-related chats, while the second run was terminated due to the already large amount of collected data.

Table 2: List of Telegram input chats.

	Chat names
Process 1	<i>NuclearDisasters, top_disasters, CatastrophicDisastersBackup, ShipDisasters, naturaldisasterbb, titanicbackup, NuclearDisasters, PlaneDisasters, disasterfreaks, WarningAlertTelegram, AlertSwiss, MeteoSwissTelegram, WarnmeldungenDeutschland, FRAlert, disaster_news, DN_Chats, warningchannels, natural_disasters</i>
Process 2	<i>hosachannel, HurricaneIan2022TheWooOfOne, Hurricane-News</i>

3.1.5 Mastodon

In contrast to most other social networks, Mastodon is a decentralised microblogging platform consisting of multiple independently hosted and moderated servers, so-called *instances* [57]. This gives users more control over their data and community policies. Mastodon’s open-source nature also allows developers to contribute to its development and create custom instances for specific interests. Research conducted on Mastodon datasets often aims to understand the strengths and weaknesses of this decentralised approach [57, 84, 40], rather than to examine content related to societal phenomena or important events. This can mainly be attributed to the platform’s relatively small user base, which is expected to grow in the future based on current trends [63].

Mastodon offers an API with a wide range of endpoints, which can be accessed e.g. through the *Mastodon.py* package. The API allows for both real-time data retrieval - capturing posts as they are shared — and historical data collection from any desired point in the past. However, a key limitation of this approach is that it necessitates retrieving all posts published within a specified time frame, requiring local rather than direct server-side filtering. The API imposes a rate limit of 300 requests per 5 minutes, with 40 posts returned per request.

We accessed 1,068,618 Mastodon posts from September 20 to October 10 2022 by requesting all posts from all Mastodon instances - from the flagship server "*mastodon.social*" and all public posts from any other instance with an interaction to the main instance - within that time range.

3.2 Geoparsing

After data acquisition, geoparsing was applied to identify and geocode locations mentioned in the textual content of the social media posts. This process began with filtering posts using the keyword "*hurricane*" to ensure a certain relatedness to the disaster in question, followed by text preprocessing to remove noise such as links, mentions, and emojis. Locations were then identified by applying spaCy’s *en_core_web_lg* model (F1 score of 0.86), and geocoded into coordinate pairs with Nominatim, an open-source geocoder based on OpenStreetMap (OSM) [68]. Consistent with previous research on Twitter data, we transformed all polygon-based locations into point representations for aggregation and visualisation purposes by calculating the centroid of each polygon [12]. We chose to use spaCy for LER because it is a resource-effective and fast approach [48] that has already been implemented and found reliable for large-scale studies. Moreover, it was trained on data from blogs, newspaper articles and comments [71], which should also ensure its suitability for use on longer social media texts such as those from Reddit.

4 Results

In our study, we gathered data from five different social media platforms. Table 3 compares the amount of originally retrieved posts to the remaining posts after keyword filtering, showing a large difference between the platforms. While we gathered more than 160,000 posts on both TikTok and Reddit containing the word "hurricane", we only identified 902 posts from Mastodon through keyword filtering. There was also a huge difference between the amount of retrieved posts and the posts relevant for the case study. In the case of Telegram, only approximately 0.02% of all collected posts mentioned the word "hurricane". For TikTok and Reddit, the keyword was already contained in the queries used for acquisition.

Table 3: Retrieved and Filtered Posts Across Platforms. In brackets, the percentage of remaining posts from the previous step is shown.

Platform	Retrieved Posts	Filtered Posts	
		Keyword filtering	+ geocoding
<i>Twitter</i>	2,798,478	24,117 (0.9%)	24,117 (100%)
<i>TikTok</i>	168,761	168,761 (100%)	113,027 (67.0%)
<i>Reddit Submissions</i>	31,187	31,187 (100%)	26,062 (83.6%)
<i>Reddit Comments</i>	169,861	169,861 (100%)	160,321 (94.4%)
<i>Telegram</i>	52 million	7,268 (0.02%)	3,294 (45.3%)
<i>Mastodon</i>	1,068,618	902 (0.08%)	474 (52.5%)

4.1 Spatial distribution

The limitation of our analysis to spatial features further reduced the amount of posts in our dataset, as not every post contained toponyms (cf. Table 3). This was particularly noticeable for Telegram and Mastodon, where only about half of the keyword-filtered posts remained after geoparsing. Further, the geocoding results revealed that most locations were rather coarse. The most frequently geocoded location was "Florida" (41,905, 46.8%), followed by "Orlando" (1,761, 2.0%), "Cuba" (1,278, 1.4%), and "Miami" (1,172, 1.3%). Table 4 lists the most common locations per platform. Additionally, there were many locations that returned valid geocoordinates, although the extracted locations were in fact no real places (e.g. "hurricaneian", "caterpillar" or "theeconomist"). There were also many hits outside of the area of interest (e.g. "ukraine"). A total of 19.1% of posts that contained a location could not be geocoded.

To better understand the spatial granularity of our geocoding results, we also extracted the bounding boxes of our identified locations via Nominatim. The calculation of their areas showed a large variance in the size of these bounding boxes. 25% of the areas were $<18.65\text{km}^2$, i.e. roughly the size of a small city. The median was $20.259.15\text{km}^2$, which corresponds approximately to the size

of Slovenia, i.e. a small country. 25% of the geocoded locations had areas $>708.716,80\text{km}^2$, which is larger than France.

Table 4: Most frequently geocoded locations per platform.

<i>TikTok</i>	<i>Reddit</i> Submissions / Comments	<i>Telegram</i>	<i>Mastodon</i>
florida (15989)	florida (2400 / 2323)	florida (1002)	florida (306)
hurricaneian (2107)	lti (1622) / fema (321)	russia (176)	cuba (38)
florida hurricaneian (1270)	caterpillar (707) / desantis (318)	ukraine (108)	nasa (29)
orlando (799)	apollo (675) / cuba (251)	south carolina (106)	atlantic (27)
miami (644)	p amp s (585) / orlando (244)	ntd (90)	theeconomist (26)

Figure 2 visualises the spatial distribution of geocoded posts for all platforms, aggregated on a 250km hexagonal grid, showing that locations all around the world were identified in the geoparsing process. Expectably, there was a clear focus on locations in the south-east of the United States. However, there were also many posts with locations in Central Europe. The figure illustrates the high diversity of locations identified in social media texts that based on pre-filtering should be related to a singular event.

Figure 4 shows the distribution for the United States with a higher spatial resolution of 100km and for each platform. While the overall patterns across platforms were very similar, the difference in post numbers per region was quite high. Particularly, Mastodon and Telegram had very few post, even in highly affected regions. In Florida, 91.0% of all counties contained at least one post (not including data from Twitter), while for the neighbouring states of South Carolina (63.0%), North Carolina (61.0%), and Georgia (34.6%), these numbers were considerably lower. On a hexagonal 50km grid, 935 grid cells contained at least one post (58.9%). On a finer 10km grid, this corresponded to only 1,200 cells (8.8%). Table 5 shows this distribution for each platform. For the fine-grained 10km grid, the relative number of cells with available data was very low for all platforms. For the larger grid, almost half of the cells had some data for TikTok and Reddit Comments. Here, it should also be mentioned that many regions of the states were not heavily affected by Hurricane Ian. Consequently, it was not surprising that some counties or grid cells did not have any substantial social media activity about the disaster.

We additionally calculated the Spearman’s correlation for the number of posts from each platform in each grid cell. For the overall dataset, correlations were between 0.17 and 0.35. However, since many locations only occurred in one dataset, these numbers were barely representative. We therefore created a subset for all grid cells intersecting the State of Florida, which was most affected by the hurricane. There, correlations between post counts were between 0.43 and 0.79, confirming the visual inspection of patterns. Figure 3 shows a correlation matrix for the subset. Only grid cells with at least one post in one platform were considered. The largest difference was found between Telegram and Mastodon posts, which was probably related to their relatively small sample sizes. Reddit comments and TikTok posts had the most correlated spatial distribution.

Table 5: Spatial coverage for the most affected states (Florida, Georgia, South Carolina, North Carolina) per platform on hexagonal grids of 10km and 50km. The count refers to the number of grid cells with at least one post.

Platform	Grid size	Count
<i>Mastodon</i>	10km	32 (0.24%)
	50km	64 (4.03%)
<i>Reddit Comments</i>	10km	739 (5.46%)
	50km	755 (47.54%)
<i>Reddit Submissions</i>	10km	459 (3.39%)
	50km	443 (27.90%)
<i>Telegram</i>	10km	139 (1.03%)
	50km	188 (11.84%)
<i>TikTok</i>	10km	771 (5.69%)
	50km	641 (40.37%)

Figure 2: Count of geoparsed posts from TikTok, Telegram, Reddit, and Mastodon on 250km hexagonal grid. Classes are inspired by natural breaks.

Figure 3: Correlation matrix (Spearman) for post counts. The datasets was filtered for grid cells in Florida.

As a baseline, we performed the same analysis for geotagged Twitter data. The aggregated spatial distribution of Tweets, based on their centroids, can be seen in Figure 4 (1). This distribution of geotagged tweets was relatively similar to TikTok and Reddit, which was also confirmed by the correlations ranging from 0.54 with Mastodon to 0.81 with TikTok and even 0.83 with Reddit comments. However, it was noticeable that there were significantly more hurricane-related Tweets in regions further away from the coastline than in the data from other platforms. The data therefore had a much stronger spatial contiguity.

Figure 4: Comparison of spatial distribution of georeferenced posts on 100km hexagonal grid.

4.2 Temporal distribution

Figure 5 illustrates the time series of geotagged posts, showing how the numbers fluctuated over time across the platforms. All platforms exhibited a peak on September 28 or 29, corresponding with the peak of the disaster, as well as the sharpest increase in the number of posts on September 26 or 27. The number of comments on Reddit had a one day temporal delay, with activity remaining slightly elevated for a longer period after the peak. Similar to the spatial distribution, we found very high correlations between the daily occurrence of posts on different platforms, with Kendall's Tau coefficients between 0.60 and 0.88 (see Figure 6). This correlation measure was chosen because the Ramsey RESET test did not provide a definitive indication for the use of either Spearman or Pearson. The highest correlation was between Reddit comments and submissions, while Telegram was the least correlated with Twitter and TikTok posts.

Figure 5: Time series of geotagged posts. Mastodon was excluded from the plot due the low amount of posts.

Figure 6: Correlation matrix (Kendall’s Tau) for post counts on daily basis.

5 Discussion

As described in Section 3.1 and Table 1, the data acquisition procedures and, thus, crawling strategies and parameter options differ heavily between the social media platforms. For this reason, the comparability of the data sets we used is somewhat limited. While this impacts the validity of our spatial analysis, raising awareness about differing selection criteria is relevant for the future use of other social media platforms in disaster-related research, as they can give rise to various biases. This also includes a selection bias, arising from the regionally different use of social media platforms. For instance, Telegram is used more in Russia than in the USA [15] and may be better suited for analyses there. More research is needed to identify which platform is most suitable for different topics and world regions. In this context, it should be emphasised that the large-scale processing of geo-social media data must always be guided by ethical and legal principles, especially with regard to data protection [20].

Our analysis revealed major differences between the various social media platforms, particularly in terms of the number of posts collected. This was especially noticeable between TikTok, Telegram, and Mastodon. This could be due to several factors: the varying number of users of the platforms, the widely differing crawling strategies, and the potential differences in content that might make some platforms more popular for disaster-related discourse. Especially for Mastodon and Telegram, we also found that most of the posts collected were irrelevant to the study. This was actually also the case for our Twitter dataset, where not even 1% of the Tweets contained the keyword “hurricane”. The computational effort involved in collecting data may therefore be disproportionate to its benefit for these platforms. Future research should focus on streamlining

data acquisition pipelines for such platforms.

Temporal patterns across platforms were quite consistent, showing similar peaks of activity. These trends coincided with Twitter, which has been shown to exhibit a higher number of Tweets in the early stage of a disaster [39]. Thus, content from other platforms could, at least from a temporal perspective, serve as a kind of substitute for Twitter. Moreover, the subtle differences suggest that certain platforms could serve complementary roles. For example, Reddit may be particularly useful in the post-disaster phase due to its extended discussions and slower decline in post activity. However, the current lack of real-time capability of TikTok and Telegram reduces their use for disaster response purposes. Future research should thus investigate how well data from alternative social media platforms can be accessed during an actual disaster scenario.

We found that one of the biggest current challenges of working with geo-social media data is the very coarse spatial resolution that can be achieved by geoparsing texts. This study showed that almost half of all successfully geocoded locations from the post texts were for the *State of Florida*. While it makes sense that the term *Florida* is featured frequently in texts related to Hurricane Ian, geolocalisation at state or even country level cannot be used to make spatially precise statements, as was previously realised with Twitter data. In addition, our analyses showed that geoparsing resulted in many incorrect geometries, as many words were erroneously recognised as locations (e.g. "hurricaneian"). This can lead to considerable distortion in the subsequent spatial analyses. The descriptive statistics based on the bounding boxes from Nominatim indicated that many geocoded locations will most likely not provide any useful spatial insights, as half of their geometries were larger than a small country. Nevertheless, it should be mentioned that much of the explicitly geo-referenced Twitter data also had a low level of spatial granularity, since many Tweet geometries were based on the 'places' attributes that often represented entire cities or regions [27, 83, 1]. In many studies, this spatial imprecision of much Twitter data has been largely ignored. Future studies should therefore consider to implement filtering to discard erroneous or very large geometries. Setting a fitting threshold for such a selection is, however, always somewhat arbitrary.

Accordingly, the spatial patterns shown in Figures 2 and 4 need to be interpreted with caution due to the described coarseness of geometries. We found that the spatial patterns between the platforms were, nevertheless, relatively similar. In particular, all had a peak in post counts for regions in Florida that were affected by the hurricane. This was also somewhat confirmed by the spatial aggregation on county-level and hexagonal grids (cf. Table 5). For individual platforms, this distribution was, however, more sparse, which supports the idea of using data from different platforms complementarily.

To enable the effective use of data from alternative social media platforms for disaster management, more complex geoparsing methods should be developed. These might take the semantic context into account during LER in order to generate spatially relevant insights. In this context, novel LLM approaches have already been proposed in several studies [42, 28]. However, LLMs are also only able to extract location mentions that are explicitly or, perhaps to a cer-

tain extent, implicitly given in the texts. Posts that do not contain any textual reference to relevant locations can thus not be identified. This was theoretically possible with Twitter data due to the detached possibility of georeferencing. Approaches based on the number of identical location mentions (by different users or on different platforms) or the co-occurrence of locations with relevant terms could also be tested to verify or improve the quality of the geometries. Future studies could also investigate whether attached imagery can be used to geocode posts or verify location mentions from their texts. Vision Language Models (VLMs) have already been proposed to identify locations in disaster-related imagery [65]. While more advanced geoparsing methods might improve the spatial granularity of social media data, a certain degree of spatial imprecision should still be expected when working with data from TikTok, Reddit, Telegram, or Mastodon.

We also compared the data from alternative platforms to a baseline of georeferenced Tweets. Based purely on the number of available Tweets, we showed that a higher number of posts with the keyword "hurricane" could be obtained via TikTok and Reddit than was possible via the Twitter API. However, it should be noted here that a more use case-specific crawling of Twitter than was carried out for this study could probably have increased these numbers. Spatial patterns of Tweets were relatively similar to other platforms, which may be due to the fact that Twitter data from 2022 was no longer based on exact GPS geometries, but on a location database. It could thus be said that the described low spatial granularity of geoparsing was already somewhat intrinsic to Twitter data.

To identify posts that were related to Hurricane Ian, we employed keyword-based filtering. To check for the validity of this rather simple semantic analysis approach, we applied the disaster-relatedness model developed by [23] to all posts in our dataset. It is a fine-tuned Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach (RoBERTa) model that categorises texts binarily. Since the model was trained on Twitter data and is thus potentially biased towards short texts, we decided to exclude the Reddit data from this evaluation. For all the other platforms, the large majority of posts was classified as disaster-related (99.1% for TikTok, 97.7% for Twitter, 93.9% for Mastodon, 92.1% for Telegram). This can be seen as an indication for the validity of our keyword filtering approach, since most of our posts were confirmed to be semantically related to natural disasters. Nevertheless, more complex semantic analysis methods should be considered for future studies, e.g. dedicated models for relevance classification [9, 35]. To ensure that such models are platform-agnostic, different text sizes should be considered in the training data, so that longer social media posts (e.g. from Reddit) can sufficiently be classified. The new generation of LLMs should, however, already be able to classify morphologically diverse texts with reduced sensitivity to structural variations.

In this first study, our focus was on the data acquisition, as well as the spatial and temporal distribution of social media posts from different platforms. In order to demonstrate a potential complementarity of the information for disaster management, semantic analyses would have to be conducted in a follow-

up study that examine the actual content, e.g. using a topic modelling approach. This could provide detailed insights into the differences in content between the platforms. It is reasonable to assume that the discourse is very much influenced by the user profile of the respective platform, i.e. its demographic distribution and political orientation.

6 Conclusion

This study investigated the suitability of data from other social media platforms than Twitter for disaster research purposes. By examining the temporal and spatial characteristics of Reddit, TikTok, Telegram, and Mastodon posts during Hurricane Ian, we explored whether data from these platforms can serve as a viable alternative to Twitter data in the future.

Our comparison to Twitter revealed general similarities in spatial and temporal distribution of hurricane-related posts. Particularly, TikTok and Reddit showed high correlations, while also having a high amount of posts. While no platform presented itself as a full substitute for Twitter due to the low spatial accuracy of geoparsing results and limited real-time capabilities (**RQ1**), we could show that a considerable amount of potentially relevant data could be acquired from other social media platforms.

While overall patterns were consistent across platforms (**RQ2**), subtle differences in temporal post activity and spatial distribution suggest that individual platforms offer unique insights that might improve situational awareness. Specifically, platforms like Reddit, with extended post-disaster discussions, and TikTok, with concentrated spatial hotspots, provided distinct contributions.

To increase the amount of available timely data and thus offer a more comprehensive view of an event for informed decision-making in disaster management, we therefore propose future studies to investigate the systematic integration of multiple data sources. This requires an in-depth concept that jointly considers the semantic, spatial and temporal dimensions of the different data to ensure its relevance to disaster management purposes [9]. More research based on use cases in different regions of the world, with other predominant languages, and with different disaster types (e.g. forest fires, earthquakes) is needed to verify the suitability of singular platforms for specific scenarios.

Currently, the biggest challenge for the application of geo-social media data in the disaster context is the low spatial accuracy that can be achieved through geoparsing. Future research therefore needs to develop new methods to make data from platforms without explicit georeferences useful for disaster management. In addition, the use of data from the presented social media platforms should be tested for topics outside the disaster context, whereby a certain bias in user distribution should be taken into account, especially for studies with a political background.

Declaration of interest

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

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